

D3.7 Research report on the survey of stakeholders

Deliverable description

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1. Introduction

Across Europe, formal commitments to universal health coverage coexist with persistent gaps in effective access for persons with disabilities. Disabled people are more than twice as likely as others to report unmet medical needs, frequently due to affordability, distance and service unavailability.

The attached cross-country survey of OPD aimed to document cost-related unmet needs for health and social care, identify the most affected services and population subgroups, and explore reasons for recourse to private care. This report addresses three research questions:

1. To what extent do respondents report cost-related unmet needs across key health and social care domains?
2. Which population groups with disabilities are perceived as most affected by cost-related barriers?
3. What are the main sources of out-of-pocket payments and the key drivers of seeking private care, and how do these patterns compare with European evidence on unmet needs and financial protection?

2. Methods

The analysis draws on an online survey distributed among European organisations of persons with disabilities and their families (OPD) because they offer a critical vantage point on these access barriers, because they aggregate experiences across diagnoses, age groups and territories and see how health and social systems interact in practice (EDF, 2019).

The survey was completed in November-December 2025 by OPD in eight European countries (Albania, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, Slovenia, Belgium, France, Italy).

The questionnaire was developed based on a review of the literature, establishing a taxonomy of clinical areas most impacted by cost barriers, population groups with the most significant unmet needs related to costs, and the causes of out-of-pocket payments among individuals with disabilities. The questionnaire consists of five quantitative questions and one open-ended query (Annex 1).

Initially, respondents rated the degree to which a series of statements on cost-related barriers applied to their members in the previous 12 months, on a 1–5 scale ranging from “not at all” to “extremely true”. Items covered medicines, medical supplies, outpatient visits,

rehabilitation, hospital and diagnostic care, dental care, mental health services, assistive devices, home adaptations, personal assistance, transport and social care.

Additional multi-response questions asked to identify:

- clinical/service areas with most unmet needs due to cost;
- population groups with the most pronounced cost-related unmet needs;
- main sources of out-of-pocket spending leading to forgone or delayed care; and
- ranked reasons for seeking private health services.

In total, 31 questionnaires (including uncompleted ones) were collected.

The data was analysed for the country-level aggregations (totals, means, medians, rankings) for key items for three countries that provided more than three responses, such as Lithuania, Latvia, Albania, and an “others” group including Belgium, Estonia, France, Italy and Slovenia. The present report uses these summary indicators descriptively and triangulates them with recent European studies and reports on unmet needs, out-of-pocket payments and disability-related access barriers. Given the modest and heterogeneous sample of OPD, the analysis is exploratory and focuses on patterns rather than formal statistical inference.

3. Findings

3.1 Overall pattern of cost-related unmet needs

Respondents assessed the veracity of statements regarding failures to satisfy health needs for their members in the preceding 12 months.

Across all countries, the highest average problem scores (≥ 3.7 on a 1–5 scale) were reported for unaffordable dental care, psychological/psychiatric care, rehabilitation, assistive devices, home adaptations and personal assistance. Items capturing core medical treatment (prescribed medicines, specialist visits, hospital/diagnostic services) also show moderate to high problem levels (averages around 2.8–3.0), indicating that cost barriers extend beyond “non-essential” services.

Internal consistency of the 15-item unmet-need scale is high (Cronbach’s alpha ≈ 0.90), supporting its interpretation as a single underlying construct of cost-related access problems. Between-country differences in the composite score are modest (Cohen’s $f \approx 0.1$,

small effect), suggesting that while profiles differ somewhat, cost pressure is a structural issue across the included health systems rather than restricted to one setting.

Across countries, OPD frequently rated cost-related barriers as “very” or “extremely” true for their members, indicating substantial unmet healthcare and social care needs. Table 1 presents the results aggregated for specific countries as well as for a residual group of other countries.

Table 1 Key figures for Albania, Latvia, Lithuania, and other countries on barriers in meeting cost-related health needs

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Albania															
median	4	4	3	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	4
percentage	7	6	5	5	6	8	6	7	7	7	8	6	7	7	7
Latvia															
median	5	5	3	1	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	4	5	5
percentage	6	6	5	3	8	8	8	8	8	6	6	6	6	6	6
Lithuania															
median	3	3	4	3	3	4	2	4	3	4	4	4	3	2	3
percentage	6	6	8	4	5	9	6	8	7	8	9	8	6	5	6
Others															
median	2	4	3	2	2	4	2	4	4	2	4	5	2	3	3
percentage	4	8	5	4	6	8	6	7	9	7	9	9	4	6	7

Where the numbers in the first row mean:

- 1 Members could not afford to buy necessary prescribed medicines,
- 2 Members could not afford to buy non-prescribed medicines,
- 3 The cost of medical supplies (e.g., catheters, wound dressings, nutritional formulas) led the members to skip or reduce use,
- 4 Members had to delay or forgo a visit to a family doctor because of the cost ,
- 5 Members had to delay or forgo a visit to a medical specialist because of the cost,
- 6 The cost of rehabilitation services (physiotherapy, occupational, speech therapy) was too high for the members' regular use,
- 7 High costs prevented members from accessing necessary hospital or diagnostic services,
- 8 Dental care (routine or urgent) was not affordable for the members,
- 9 Psychological counseling or psychiatric treatment was unaffordable due to out-of-pocket costs,
- 10 Members were not able to purchase or repair necessary assistive devices (e.g., mobility/communication aids) due to cost,
- 11 Home adaptations needed for independent living (e.g., ramps, accessible bathroom) were out of financial reach for the members,
- 12 The costs of personal assistance or home nursing services were a barrier for members,
- 13 Members missed medical appointments or therapies because they could not afford transportation needing support,
- 14 Members used savings or went into debt to afford essential healthcare,
- 15 Members can not afford essential social care

Note: “Median” represent the median values for each item; higher scores indicate that the respective barrier is perceived as more significant. The percentage indicates the distribution of total responses across all items within a specific country or group of countries.

In the aggregated indicators, Albania (N8) show consistently high average scores (mean 3.9, SE 0.16) for cost-related problems across almost all domains, while Lithuania (N13) shows moderate but still significant levels (mean 3.2, SE 0.2), and Latvia (N4) displays a particularly severe profile for several services (mean 4.4, SE 0.57). The mean 3.0, SE 0.41, for other countries (N6) was slightly lower.

Figure 1 Comparisons of medians in perceiving barriers in meeting cost-related health needs

Note: Numbers on vertical axis present the scores on the 1-5 Likert scale scale from “not at all” to “extremely” true. Numbers on horizontal axis present the answers form 1 to 15 listed explanations for the Table 1.

These patterns mirror European evidence that unmet needs and financial hardship are particularly high in Eastern and South-Eastern Europe, where out-of-pocket payments finance a substantial share of health expenditure and coverage gaps are more pronounced. (Maslyankov, 2024; WHO Regional Office for Europe. C. 2023)

Figure 1 illustrates the medians among countries and barriers. Averages for Lithuania suggest moderate difficulty affording prescribed and non-prescribed medicines (around 2.5–3), higher barriers for dental care, assistive devices, home adaptations and personal assistance (around 3–4), and substantial reliance on savings or debt to pay for essential care (around 2–3). In contrast, in Latvia and Albania the corresponding averages often approach or exceed 4–5, indicating that medicines, rehabilitation, dental care, assistive devices,

personal assistance and transport are “very” or “extremely” unaffordable for many disabled people. This aligns with broader EU and WHO data showing that pharmaceuticals, dental care and long-term care are the key drivers of out-of-pocket spending, and that financial hardship from these costs is common among people with chronic conditions and disabilities. (WHO Regional Office for Europe. C, 2023; OECD, 2023). Respondents from other countries perceived that the costs of personal assistance or home nursing services were the most substantial barrier.

3.2 Access to service most affected by cost

Answers to the second question “In which clinical/service areas do your members most frequently report unmet needs due to cost?” allowed us to rank which clinical and service areas are unaffordable most frequently.

When asked to select specific clinical/service areas with unmet need due to cost, respondents most frequently pointed to rehabilitation therapies, home care/personal assistance, dental care, mental health services and assistive devices. In Lithuania, for example, home care/personal assistance and assistive devices are repeatedly selected, while general practitioner care is rarely identified as a primary cost-related unmet need area. In Albania, the pattern emphasises combined gaps in rehabilitation, mental health, dental care and home care, reflecting limited public coverage and high Out-of-Pocket Payments (OOP) spending for long-term support.

Both our survey and European studies highlight a cluster of services where cost-related unmet needs are most acute for people with disabilities:

- **Medicines** (especially non-reimbursed products and those with high co-payments). OPDs in several countries emphasise difficulty affording essential medications, including insulin, continuous glucose monitoring sensors and newer chronic disease therapies. This matches evidence that out-of-pocket spending on pharmaceuticals accounts for a large share of household health expenditure across EU countries. (WHO Regional Office for Europe. A, 2023; OECD, 2024)
- **Rehabilitation and long-term therapies.** Respondents repeatedly note limited coverage of physiotherapy, occupational and speech therapy, strict caps on sessions, and the need to pay privately for additional or specialised rehabilitation. Systematic reviews for

South-Eastern Europe similarly find high unmet needs for rehabilitation and long-term care, driven by underfunding and limited benefit packages. (Maslyankov, 2024)

- **Dental and mental health care.** Dental care and psychological or psychiatric treatment are often described as unaffordable, leading to delayed or forgone care. Regional surveys confirm that unmet needs are particularly high for dental and mental health services across Europe, especially among younger adults and vulnerable groups. (Eurofound. A, 2025).
- **Assistive devices and home adaptations.** Several OPD stress that wheelchairs, communication aids and tracheostomy supplies are insufficiently reimbursed or only cheap, low-quality products are covered; home adaptations such as ramps and accessible bathrooms frequently require large out-of-pocket contributions. EU and disability-focused reviews identify inadequate coverage of assistive technologies and home modifications as a pervasive barrier to independent living and participation. ([World Health Organization Regional Office for Europe. B, 2023)
- **Personal assistance, home care and transport.** Respondents report that publicly financed hours of personal assistance are very limited, that care involving intimate hygiene is particularly hard to obtain, and that specialised transport is both scarce and expensive, leading to social isolation. European analyses similarly point to insufficient publicly funded long-term care and high transport costs as major contributors to unmet social care and healthcare needs among disabled people. (EASPD, 2018; WHO Centre for Health Development, 2022; European Commission, 2021)

Specifically, the most frequently unaffordable areas (with maximum ranks) were identified as follows:

- in Albania (N7) – 1. dental care, 2. rehabilitation, 3. mental and home care (in diminishing order);
- in Latvia (N3) – prescribed medicines, medical consultation and hospital services, rehabilitation and home care;
- in Lithuania (N11) – 1. rehabilitation, 2. home care, 3. dental care and assistive devices (in diminishing order);
- and in the other countries (N5) – mental, dental and home care.

3.3 Most affected population groups

The multi-response question on population groups shows a clear hierarchy of perceived vulnerability across the sample. Aggregated scores indicate that in the full dataset, children with disabilities, people with multiple or complex disabilities, and persons living below the national poverty line/very low income are the most frequently flagged as facing cost-related unmet needs, followed by older adults with disabilities and rural residents. Rural residents are repeatedly mentioned in Albania and Lithuania, where transport costs and lack of local services add a geographic access layer to financial barriers.

Country-specific rankings show:

- Lithuania: highest scores for children with disabilities, people with multiple/complex disabilities, and persons below the poverty line, with substantial concern also for older adults and rural residents.
- Latvia: older adults with disabilities and people with complex disabilities rank highest, alongside low-income groups, while explicit mention is made of people with chronic diseases without a formal disability status who nonetheless face high costs.
- Albania: cost-related unmet needs are seen as pervasive across all disability age groups and strongly concentrated among people in poverty.

These patterns align with European data showing that people with disabilities, especially those with low income, limited education and multiple functional limitations, experience much higher rates of unmet medical needs than the general population. Older people with disabilities and multimorbidity are particularly exposed to cost-induced unmet needs, especially for specialist and long-term care. (Krutilova, 2021; Rahman, 2022)

3.4 Qualitative insights on lived experience

People with disabilities and their families describe pervasive cost and access barriers that make it difficult or impossible to secure essential care, particularly personal assistance, rehabilitation, medicines, assistive supplies, and transport. These barriers cut across countries and settings and often combine with disrespectful treatment and system failures, amplifying emotional and financial hardship.

Respondents highlight severe shortages and underfunding of **personal assistance**, especially for intimate and continuous care. One contribution notes that “personal assistance, care that needs personal hygiene aspects is most difficult to obtain, as number of hours and hourly reimbursed cost is very low, there are nobody to become assistant.” Night-time respite is described as virtually unavailable: “To get any service for overnight (so caregiver could sleep) is impossible.”

Home-based nursing and support are reported as both scarce and largely out-of-pocket. A Lithuanian caregiver explains that “home help almost does not exist..., you have to pay for nursing at home”. Families caring for adults with severe disability also face high uncovered costs for tracheostomy care supplies and other consumables needed for daily survival.

Rehabilitation is repeatedly described as underfunded and insufficient in intensity and duration, especially for people with severe disabilities. One Lithuanian case reports that adults with severe disability requiring a companion “experience a significant financial burden in order to benefit from inpatient medical rehabilitation services,” because the sickness fund covers only the basic package and “all expenses related to the accommodation of the accompanying person are paid by the disabled person out of his/her own pocket.” Limited publicly covered rehabilitation sessions leave substantial unmet needs as well.

For children with autism and other neurodevelopmental conditions, the lack of funded therapies is particularly striking. An Albanian organization reports a family “who has 2 twins with autism and have never been able to send them in therapy ... The family was not supported from the social care.” Another OPD notes avoiding private rehabilitation and psychological care altogether “because of prices.”

Stories underscore major gaps in coverage for **medicines and essential supplies**, even in systems with formal reimbursement. One respondent points to “medicine that is available worldwide and not reimbursed by health insurance” as “another big issue.” In Lithuania, the temporary breakdown of the e-health system (eSveikata) meant that “essential medications were not possible to purchase,” illustrating how digital failures can abruptly block access to treatment.

Several narratives describe low-quality but compensated products that effectively leave needs unmet. A Lithuanian respondent observes that catheters from one reimbursed producer are “so low quality… that it equals to having none.” For complex needs such as enteral feeding, families may face total lack of public coverage: “When my child got implemented gastrostomy tube I found out that none of the enteral supplies were covered. I had to look for financial support to be able to use enteral feeding devices and special enteral food.” OPDs representing people with diabetes report long-standing unresolved issues around paying for continuous glucose monitoring sensors, insulin pumps and accessories, intravitreal injections, insulin needles, and newer SGLT-2 (Sodium-Glucose Cotransporter-2 Inhibitors) and GLP-1 (Glucagon-Like Peptide-1 Receptor Agonists) medications.

Transition to adulthood and **life course gaps** are also highlighted by the respondents. Several testimonies emphasize sharp discontinuities in coverage when children with disabilities reach adulthood. A Lithuanian OPD describes that when the child turned 18 with severe disability, “many things are no longer reimbursed, medicines become difficult to obtain, copayments are large, waiting times long, and many buildings are inaccessible”. This transition is experienced as a sudden withdrawal of support at a time when needs often remain constant or increase.

OPDs also stress the long-term perspective: one Albanian OPD recounts the children’s struggle to access an assistant teacher and the parents’ efforts to teach children to read and write, then notes the current difficulty in securing employment support. In conclusion, it is stated that “we cannot change these people, we must change the world for these children,” highlighting both structural barriers and parental concern about their children’s future independence when they are no longer there to help.

Transport emerges as a major indirect cost that effectively rations access to services. One Albanian contribution notes that because services for people with disabilities “especially in rural areas, are not provided,” the cost of travelling to urban centres “burdens family budgets.” A Latvian example describes how a disability transport allowance is so limited that it “is enough for a maximum of two trips with special transport to reach a doctor”, and reports that many intercity buses now have high steps and no wheelchair access, making them unusable for wheelchair users and parents with strollers.

Beyond financial and physical barriers, respondents recount **experiences of stigma and neglect** within health facilities. During the pandemic, Albanian OPD describes a disabled adult with new mental health problems who was admitted to a psychiatric hospital and “was not perceived as a person in need of medical care and support, but as a burden on society, and even on the medical staff themselves.” The OPD calls this attitude “completely unworthy of healthcare professionals” and describes it as “one of the biggest emotional blows ever experienced.” These stories illustrate how cost and coverage gaps interact with discriminatory attitudes and fragile service organization to produce profound unmet health needs for people with disabilities and their families.

3.5 The out-of-pocket costs

The decomposition of OOP cost drivers shows a mix of formal and informal mechanisms generating financial hardship. In Lithuania, the highest-ranked sources include full charges for services not publicly covered, costs of non-reimbursed medicines and medical supplies, and gaps in coverage for assistive devices, with high transport costs also playing a significant role. In Albania, virtually all listed sources contribute: private provider charges, formal co-payments, full charges for non-covered services, and costs of devices, supplies and transport all receive multiple endorsements, reflecting a fragmented and shallow coverage environment. Latvia’s small sample highlights costs of specialized transport and diabetes-related technologies and medicines as particularly problematic, including continuous glucose monitoring sensors, insulin pumps and some newer antidiabetic agents. Across all “other” countries (Italy, Slovenia, Estonia, Belgium, France, Japan), formal co-payments in both health and social sectors, non-covered services, and transport again emerge as recurrent sources of OOP burden. Figure 2 illustrates the three to five major sources of OOP pressure across the countries.

Figure 2 Ranking of the OOPs' sources (3-5) mostly influenced unmet health needs

Note: the highest number means most significant OOPs pressure source.

Analysis of answers to the question “What are the main sources of out-of-pocket costs that cause members to forgo or delay needed care?” by country indicates that several types of payments contribute to forgone or delayed care;

- Full charges for services not covered by public financing (e.g. private rehabilitation, psychotherapy, certain diagnostics and home care) are among the most frequently selected cost sources in all three focal European countries (Lithuania, Latvia, Albania) and in the “others” group.
- Limited coverage or high deductibles in public schemes, and insufficient provision of needed services requiring private payment, are also prominent, particularly in Lithuania and Albania.
- Costs of medicines not reimbursed or only partially reimbursed, and of medical supplies and assistive devices not covered by public payers, are repeatedly identified as major drivers of financial strain.
- High transportation costs, especially for specialised or accessible transport, are repeatedly emphasised in Latvia and Lithuania, where respondents link transport costs to social isolation and inability to attend family or community events.

These survey results align with broader European evidence on financial protection, which indicates that out-of-pocket payments in EU countries often arise for outpatient visits, diagnostics, dental care, rehabilitation, long-term care, pharmaceuticals, and transport, and that such payments can be catastrophic for low-income and disabled households. (Arsenijevic, 2016, WHO Regional Office for Europe.C. 2023)

3.6 Reasons for using private health-related services

Respondents ranked six potential reasons for using private health services and revealed a consistent hierarchy across countries. Figure 3 depicts the predominant reasons for seeking private health services across various countries.

Median rankings for Lithuania, Latvia, Albania and the “others” group suggest that:

- Long waiting times in the public sector and the absence or unavailability of desired services are central reasons for seeking private care in all three European focus countries.
- In Lithuania, higher quality or choice in the private sector and lack of public sector expertise for specific disabilities also feature prominently, with “absence of desired service in the public sector” ranked as the most important reason in the national median ranking.
- In Latvia, long waiting times and higher quality/choice in the private sector dominate, with a lack of public sector expertise also important.
- In Albania, the scarcity of public services at the local level and long waiting times are key drivers, alongside perceived better quality or availability in private facilities.

Figure 3 Ranking of the most prevalent reasons for seeking private services

Note: the highest number (5) means most prevalent reason.

Median rankings indicate that “other” reasons (open-ended) are systematically placed last, underscoring that structural gaps in availability and timeliness, rather than idiosyncratic preferences, drive recourse to private care. This pattern suggests an implicit two-tier system in which those able to pay privately circumvent public system bottlenecks, while others face prolonged unmet need.

These findings resonate with European analyses that emphasise long waiting lists, inadequate geographic availability of services (especially in rural areas), and perceived quality differentials as major determinants of unmet needs and recourse to private care. In contexts where public coverage is incomplete, disabled people often face a choice between long delays in the public system or unaffordable private care, which can lead either to distress spending or to forgone care (EASPD, 2019).

4. Discussion

The survey of disability organisations paints a coherent picture of multi-dimensional access barriers driven by both financial and supply-side constraints. Respondents’ reports of high out-of-pocket spending for medicines, rehabilitation, dental and mental health care, assistive devices, home adaptations and personal assistance closely match European comparative findings on where benefit packages are weakest and user charges most prevalent. The strong emphasis on transport barriers, particularly specialised transport, also aligns with EU-wide evidence that distance and lack of accessible public transport contribute significantly to unmet needs among disabled people (Moran, 2021; Eurofound. B. 2025; EASPD, 2018).

The profile of affected groups—children with disabilities, people with multiple/complex disabilities, older disabled adults and those living in poverty—mirrors the social gradient in health and financial protection documented across Europe. Several respondents explicitly describe situations in which disability benefits are the only income source in multi-person households, making even modest co-payments or transport costs prohibitive. This echoes WHO analyses showing that even small out-of-pocket amounts can be unaffordable for low

-income and high-need households, leading to care being postponed or skipped (Thomson, 2024; WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2023).

The survey also highlights the tight interconnection between health and social care. Home adaptations, personal assistance, and social care services are routinely described as underfunded and requiring substantial household payments, despite being essential to prevent institutionalisation and enable participation. European research shows that unmet social care needs, particularly assistance with activities of daily living, are widespread and strongly associated with disability, functional limitations and low income. (WHO Centre for Health Development, 2023).

A major **strength** of this survey is its grounding in the perspectives of OPD, which aggregate experiences across multiple members and are well placed to identify systemic barriers, including those at the interface of health and social sectors. The instrument encompasses a broad range of services and cost sources, providing a nuanced understanding of where benefit packages and financing arrangements fall short for people with disabilities. The inclusion of open-ended narratives provides rich qualitative detail that contextualises the quantitative indicators, for example, by illustrating the cumulative financial burden of multiple uncovered items such as enteral feeding supplies, specialised transport and private personal assistance.

However, several **limitations** must be acknowledged. First, the sample is relatively small and heterogeneous across countries, and may not be representative of all disability organisations or of disabled individuals more broadly in each country. Second, the survey relies on organisational perceptions rather than individual-level data; while this offers a valuable advocacy perspective, it may introduce reporting biases and cannot be directly compared with population surveys such as EU-SILC or WHO e-surveys. Third, the cross-sectional design and absence of detailed socio-demographic data limit the ability to disaggregate by type of disability, gender, or income, which are known to shape unmet needs. Finally, cross-country comparisons are constrained by small sample sizes and possible differences in how organisations interpret the rating scales and items.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

Organisations of persons with disabilities across several European countries report substantial cost-related unmet needs for healthcare and social support, particularly for medicines, rehabilitation, dental and mental health care, assistive technologies, home adaptations, personal assistance and transport. These barriers disproportionately affect children and older adults with disabilities, people with multiple or complex disabilities, and those living in poverty, and they interact with long waiting times and limited local availability of services to drive recourse to private care or outright forgone care.

The survey identifies genuine structural weaknesses in health and social protection for people with disabilities. Thus, the following policy implications are as follows:

- to strengthen financial protection for disability-relevant services (pharmaceuticals, rehabilitation, assistive technologies, long-term care, transport);
- to address non-financial access barriers such as long waiting times, limited local availability and lack of provider expertise in disability; and
- to ensure that disability-related benefits and social assistance are adequate to cover the extra costs of disability, and that means-tested exemptions effectively reach low-income disabled households.

In light of the survey findings and the wider European literature, the following recommendations are proposed:

Expand coverage and reduce user charges for disability-relevant services

- Remove or substantially reduce co-payments for essential medicines, particularly for chronic and high-cost therapies used by disabled people and children.
- Integrate rehabilitation, mental health care and dental care for disabled people into core benefit packages with adequate volume limits, avoiding restrictive caps that push patients into private markets.

Strengthen financing for assistive technologies, home adaptations and long-term care

- Ensure full or near-full coverage of high-quality assistive devices and necessary medical supplies, including wheelchairs, communication aids and tracheostomy and enteral feeding equipment.
- Introduce or expand grants or subsidies for home adaptations to make independent living feasible, particularly for people with severe mobility or cognitive impairments.

- Increase publicly funded hours and hourly rates for personal assistance and home nursing, with specific provisions for intimate care and overnight support where needed.

Improve **geographic accessibility** and transport support

- Develop disability-inclusive transport policies, including accessible public transport standards and targeted transport subsidies for disabled people, especially in rural areas.
- Align health and social sector planning to ensure that key services (rehabilitation, mental health, specialised clinics) are available within a reasonable travel distance, reducing reliance on expensive private or long-distance care.

Ensure **target protection** for high-risk groups

- Prioritise financial and service coverage improvements for children with disabilities, people with multiple/complex disabilities, and low-income disabled households, using disability-sensitive poverty and needs assessments.
- Ensure that people with substantial functional limitations but without formal disability status are not excluded from fee exemptions or targeted benefits.

Integrate disability-inclusive **monitoring** into health and social data systems

- Incorporate disability identifiers and indicators of unmet needs and financial hardship into routine health and social care information systems and surveys, enabling regular tracking of progress.
- Institutionalise structured engagement with OPD in policy design, implementation and evaluation to capture emerging access problems and co-produce solutions.

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Annex 1 - Questionnaire

Cost-Related Unmet Health Needs for People with Disabilities

The questions below focus on the experiences of your organization's members regarding affordability barriers across a broad range of clinical and support areas. Notably, if you have summaries of experiences or stories that received strong reactions—such as those that touched you deeply or sparked important discussion—please share them.

Responses will be kept confidential and analyzed collectively.

1. For each statement, please indicate how true it is for your members in need in the past 12 months: Not at all true, Slightly true, Moderately true, Very true, Extremely true.

- Members could not afford to buy necessary prescribed medicines
- Members could not afford to buy non-prescribed medicines
- The cost of medical supplies (e.g., catheters, wound dressings, nutritional formulas) led the members to skip or reduce use
- Members had to delay or forgo a visit to a family doctor because of the cost
- Members had to delay or forgo a visit to a medical specialist because of the cost
- The cost of rehabilitation services (physiotherapy, occupational, speech therapy) was too high for the members' regular use
- High costs prevented members from accessing necessary hospital or diagnostic services
- Dental care (routine or urgent) was not affordable for the members
- Psychological counseling or psychiatric treatment was unaffordable due to out-of-pocket costs
- Members were not able to purchase or repair necessary assistive devices (e.g., mobility/communication aids) due to cost
- Home adaptations needed for independent living (e.g., ramps, accessible bathroom) were out of financial reach for the members
- The costs of personal assistance or home nursing services were a barrier for members
- Members missed medical appointments or therapies because they could not afford transportation needing support

- Members used savings or went into debt to afford essential healthcare
- Members can not afford essential social care
- Other (Please specify)

2. In which clinical/service areas do your members most frequently report unmet needs due to cost? (Select up to five)

- Purchasing prescribed medications
- Purchasing non-prescribed medicines
- Medical specialist consultations (e.g., neurology, cardiology)
- Rehabilitation therapies (e.g., physiotherapy, occupational therapy, speech therapy)
- Mental health services (e.g., counseling, psychiatry)
- Dental care (routine, urgent)
- General practitioner/Family doctor visits
- Hospital services and diagnostics (e.g., imaging, lab tests)
- Assistive devices/equipment (e.g., wheelchair, hearing aid)
- Home care/personal assistance
- Transportation to and from healthcare appointments
- Other (please specify)

3. For which population groups are cost-related unmet needs most pronounced? (Select all that apply)

- Children with disabilities
- Working-age adults with disabilities
- Older adults with disabilities
- People with multiple or complex disabilities
- Rural residents
- Urban residents
- Ethnic minorities
- Persons living below national poverty line/very low income
- Migrants or refugees
- Other (please specify)

4. Please add any personal stories or examples that you feel could help us better understand these issues. "Native language" is welcome. Additionally, feel free to provide references to any source that is available to the public (e.g., open-access articles, public reports, official websites, or open messages)

5. What are the main sources of out-of-pocket costs that cause members to forgo or delay needed care? (Select up to five)

- Private sector provider charges
- Official co-payments in the public healthcare sector
- Official co-payments in the public social sector
- Informal or "unofficial" charges in the public healthcare sector
- Informal or "unofficial" charges in the public social sector
- Full charges for services not covered by public financing schemes
- Limited coverage or high deductibles in public financing schemes
- Insufficient provision of needed services (requiring private payment)
- Costs of medicines not reimbursed or partially reimbursed
- Costs for medical supplies not covered by public payer
- Costs for assistive devices not covered by public payer
- High transportation costs
- Other (please specify)

6. If members seek private health services, what are the main reasons? Please rank the reasons for seeking private health services from most to least important by clicking the up and down arrow buttons next to each option. Move your preferred reason to the top, and continue ordering the rest accordingly. Each option should have a unique position.

- Needed public services are unavailable locally
- Long waiting times in public sector
- Higher quality or choice in the private sector
- Lack of public sector expertise in specific disability/condition
- Absence of desired service in public sector
- Other (please specify)

7. Please say us in which country is your organization based?